

THE SCIENCE OF ENDOCRINOLOGY, HISTORY OF ITS ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Endocrinology (endo and Greek. kopet - separation and...logy) is a branch of clinical medicine. It studies the structure, development, and functions of the endocrine glands, the hormones they produce, and diseases associated with them.

Keywords: progesterone, thyroxine, adrenaline, triiodothyronine, oxytocin, vasopressin

Endocrinology as a science was formed in the second half of the 19th century. The German physiologist A. Berthold removed the testicles of roosters or transferred them to young roosters, in which various physiological and morphological changes occurred in the inseminated rooster. This was the first experiment in the field of E. (1849).

Initially, the concept of internal secretion glands was put forward by the German physiologist and naturalist D. Müller (1830), but it was introduced into the science as a term by the French physiologist C. Bernard (1855). During these periods, the Irishman R. Graves (1835) and the German scientist K. Bazedov (1840) described diffuse toxic goiter, and the English doctor T. Addison (1855) described the clinic of chronic adrenal insufficiency. Swiss surgeon Theodor Kocher (1841 - 1917) developed a surgical method for the treatment of diffuse toxic goiter. In 1889-1990s, German scientists D. Mering and O. Minkovsky experimentally determined that diabetes is a disorder of the pancreas, and Russian scientist L. V. Sobolev (1901) determined that the internal secretion of the pancreas is related to pancreatic islets (islets of Langerhans). It was later discovered by Canadian researchers F. Banting and Ch. It was the scientific basis for Best's isolation of the insulin hormone from the pancreas (1921). By the beginning of the 20th century, Endocrinology developed as a science. Many hormones were isolated: adrenaline (1901), thyroxine (1915), progesterone, testosterone (1934), corticosteroids (1937-52), triiodothyronine (1950), oxytocin and vasopressin (1953); determination of the chemical structure of hormones became the basis for their synthesis, and later for the development of their biologically active analogues several times higher than various natural hormones. The development of this science in Uzbekistan began with the investigation of goitre, which is widespread among the population, and the identification of iodine

deficiency in its origin. 30th Endemic smallpox was studied in each region of Uzbekistan with the help of different groups and expeditions (S. A. Masumov, P. I. Fedorova, Yo. Kh. Torakulov, Sh. Sh. Ilyasov, V. N. Fedoseyev, T. M. Muhamedov, etc.). In order to prevent this disease, in 1954, a smallpox dispensary was established in Tashkent, and based on epidemiological and preventive work on thyroid diseases, it was determined that it is necessary to provide the population with table salt with potassium iodide salt.

Endemic goiter and the study and treatment of other diseases of the thyroid gland are an important scientific and social problem for our country, which determined the main direction of the Institute of Scientific Research of National Medicine, established in 1957 within the framework of Uzbekistan. In 1989, the Institute of Endocrinology was established on the basis of the National Medical Research Institute. R. Q. Islambekov, Yo. H. Torakulov was the first in the world to develop a new method of diagnosis and treatment of goiter and received a prestigious award (1964). The results of biochemical, pathophysiological and clinical morphological indicators of the thyroid gland obtained in normal, thyroid pathology and radioiodine therapy gave positive results.

In 1998, a large-scale epidemiological study of iodine deficiency cases was conducted in the republic, and its average prevalence was determined. The method of cryopreservation of endocrine glands (thyroid gland, parathyroid gland and adrenal gland) in liquid nitrogen and treatment of patients with its deficiency by transplantation was developed and put into practice. For the first time, a cryopreserved tissue bank was established in the Central Asian countries (which stores about 1000 tissues). New methods of biochemical, genetic and morphological examination of thyroid gland cancer were introduced, and an algorithm for the use

of surgical, radiological and conservative therapy methods was developed (prof. S. I. Ismailov). The immunological system of patients with diffuse toxic goiter and moderately acute thyroiditis was studied, and changes and dynamics of these indicators were determined in different methods of treatment. Based on the epidemiology and etiopathogenesis of diabetes and its complications, the importance of genetic factors, the internal and external factors predisposing to the spread of the disease were comprehensively studied, and methods of limiting them and teaching patients to control their condition were developed (prof. Z. S. Akbarov).

Current problems and main areas of modern endocrinology are diabetes, thyroid gland diseases, gonadal dysfunction, hypothalamohypophyseal system diseases, primary hyperparathyroidism problem, study of the mechanism of action of hormones in the body, biosynthesis and their exchange, development of hormone analogs and new hormonal drugs, etc. k. consists of Delay in physical development remains one of the most important problems of children's endocrinology. Now. Currently, a special program for congenital anomalies screening has been launched in Uzbekistan. Neuroendocrinology is being formed as an independent department of endocrinology.

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